

Structural Fire Resistance of Partially Restrained, Partially Composite Floor Beams, I: Experiments

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Abstract

This paper is Part 1 of a two-part investigation of the structural fire resistance of a partially composite, one-way spanning steel floor beam assembly with partial translational and rotational end restraint provided by shear tab connections to a supporting frame. The goal of this study is to provide experimental data and validated numerical models that can aid the implementation of performance-based design and evaluation approaches for structural fire resistance of steel-framed composite floor systems that are typical of North American building practice. This paper describes a pair of experimental tests on structurally identical composite floor specimens that are subjected to fire via a large modular furnace. A subsequent companion paper (Part 2) presents the numerical studies. One specimen was designed to conform to a 2-hr fire rating as prescribed by UL Design No. D902 – the other was tested with no passive fire protection (i.e. as bare steel). Both specimens were flexurally loaded and tested to structural failure under exposure to the ASTM E119 standard fire, and the experimental results are evaluated using the ASTM E119 thermal and structural failure criteria. The test results show similar correlations of midspan deflection to beam temperature for both specimens. The shear tab connections experienced permanent deformation but maintained adequate structural integrity to allow the specimens to reach flexural failure. Neither shear slip nor localized cracking could be visibly detected at the composite stud locations during post-test inspection, indicating that composite action was maintained up to flexural failure.

30

31 **Keywords: fire resistance; composite steel floor beams; passive fire protection; performance-**
32 **based design**

33

34 **1. Introduction**

35 A significant segment of the worldwide steel building inventory utilizes composite floor
36 systems with rectilinear framing layouts. These systems typically consist of wide-flange steel
37 beams (i.e. secondary framing) which support a reinforced concrete floor slab. Bolted shear
38 connections are used to support the beam from adjacent girders or columns (i.e. primary framing).
39 Composite action between the beam and slab is typically achieved using headed studs that are
40 welded to the top flange of the beam prior to the placement of the slab. The current practice for
41 fire-resistant design of these floor systems is predominantly prescribed in the building code based
42 on the size, occupancy, and function of the structure [1]. If required, passive fire protection
43 consisting of encasement or coating materials is applied to the floor beams to mitigate their
44 temperature increase during a fire. For the majority of composite floor systems in the US, passive
45 fire protection consists of spray-applied fire resistive material (SFRM) which is field applied to
46 the floor beams as an approximately contoured layer.

47 Based on their occupancy and dimensions, many steel buildings are required to have
48 passive fire protection applied to their structural elements in accordance with specified hourly
49 ratings per the 2018 International Building Code [1]. These fire resistance ratings are developed
50 from the results of experimental tests referred to as “standard” fire tests, among them ASTM E119
51 [2], ANSI/UL 263 [3], and ISO 834 [4]. For standard fire tests of composite floor assemblies, the
52 specimen is subjected to a “standard” fire consisting of a relatively rapid temperature increase

53 followed by a long period of slowly increasing high temperature up to a maximum of 1260°C (i.e.
54 with no decay phase, the specimen will eventually reach failure). In these tests, the application of
55 loading beyond self-weight is optional, and the hourly rating for structural steel members can be
56 determined as the time at which the steel beam reaches a prescribed limit of maximum or average
57 temperature. These thermal criteria implicitly rate the specimen's ability to maintain structural
58 integrity by limiting the losses of the steel beam's strength and stiffness. In these tests, a floor
59 assembly can also be directly evaluated for its ability to maintain structural integrity by supporting
60 a constantly applied flexural load while heated. As its temperature increases, the specimen's
61 deflection can increase up to prescribed limits for total deflection and rate of deflection. Applied
62 loads should represent the "maximum-load condition allowed under nationally recognized
63 structural design criteria unless limited design criteria are specified and a corresponding reduced
64 load is applied" [2]. However, the descriptions of fire resistant building assemblies in resources
65 such as the UL product specification catalog [5] will often not identify whether thermal or
66 deflection-based criteria was used to develop the hourly ratings if both would apply. If deflection-
67 based criteria are used, the load used to test the assemblies is also not explicitly stated.

68 A composite steel beam floor system subassembly can be tested either with full axial and
69 rotational restraint at its ends (i.e. "restrained) or with no axial or rotational restraint (i.e.
70 "unrestrained"). In North American construction practice, fire protection requirements for floor
71 systems in steel buildings are correspondingly classified as either restrained or unrestrained to
72 thermal expansion. The restrained/unrestrained classification was first included in the ASTM E119
73 standard in 1970 to address questions about how the boundary conditions of tested specimens
74 could be translated to actual designs of building floors and roofs [6]. Experimental studies over
75 the past 50 years (as summarized by Gewain and Troup [6]) have generally supported the

76 expectation that providing at least some restraint to composite floor specimen under fire will have
77 greater fire resistance versus an unrestrained specimen due to structural redundancy and continuity.
78 The ASTM E119 standard recognizes this expectation by allowing performance limits that are
79 slightly more liberal for restrained specimens than unrestrained specimens [7] – as a result,
80 restrained assemblies typically require less passive fire protection than their unrestrained
81 counterparts to achieve the same hourly rating. In actual systems, the level of rotational and axial
82 restraint provided to most heated floor assemblies will not match either condition used in the
83 standard test due to the effects of beam end connections and the finite stiffness of the surrounding
84 structure [7], although the performance of floor systems in many steel buildings will trend toward
85 restrained [6,8]. Both ASTM E119 [2] and the building code [1] stipulate that engineering
86 judgment must be exercised to determine whether the surrounding or supporting structure is
87 sufficient to restrain thermal expansion – there is currently no standardized method for establishing
88 a level of sufficient restraint in the actual structure to correlate to the standard fire test results.

89 Due to the size limitations of most test facilities, standard fire tests are often performed at
90 modest span lengths with smaller beam sections and idealized end conditions. Since most
91 composite floor assemblies in the field will not exactly match those tested, guidance for translating
92 the fire protection requirements from the tested specimens (such as those documented in the UL
93 catalog [5]) to an actual structure is provided in references such as ASCE/SEI/SFPE 29-05 [9] and
94 AISC Design Guide 19 [10]. The protection thickness needed to achieve a prescribed hourly rating
95 for a particular beam section is calculated by comparing its ratio of cross-sectional area to fire-
96 exposed perimeter (W/D) against that of the tested section. Though straightforward, this approach
97 to calculating equivalent insulation thickness is thermally focused and not necessarily a direct
98 indicator of structural performance [6,8], which is influenced by variations in the level of applied

99 loading, span length, steel section size, slab properties, the degree of composite action, and beam
100 end conditions.

101 If equipped with the relevant input and guidance, structural engineers can utilize
102 performance-based approaches to have greater participation in designing composite floor systems
103 for fire loading. Performance-based approaches provide a quantitative assessment of the response
104 of structural members to fire exposure via thermo-mechanical calculations. Performance-based
105 design provisions for structural fire resistance of steel buildings have been a part of the Eurocode
106 [11,12] for more than a decade and are also now included in Appendix 4 of AISC 360-16 [13],
107 Appendix E of ASCE 7-16 [14], and ASCE's newly released Manual of Practice 138 for structural-
108 fire engineering [15]. The implementation of these resources in practice is dependent on the
109 development of validated structural-fire calculation approaches. An expert panel assembled in
110 2012 by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) identified large-scale
111 structural testing of composite floor systems under fire as a major research need to address the
112 structural ambiguities in the current approaches for their fire resistant design [16]. If made widely
113 available, thermal and structural data from standard fire tests on composite floor assemblies can
114 serve as validation benchmarks for modeling approaches that appropriately account for realistic
115 restraint of thermal expansion, quantify the thermo-mechanical response and factor of safety, and
116 evaluate resilience to realistic fires that include a decay phase to burnout [17].

117 This project contributes to the development of a performance-based framework for fire
118 resistant design of composite steel floor beam systems with a pair of large-scale experimental tests
119 and associated numerical modeling. This paper (Part 1) documents the experimental phase of the
120 project, while a companion paper (Part 2 [18]) outlines the numerical validation and modeling.
121 The two tests utilize structurally identical specimens that are typical of North American composite

122 floor construction, with wide-flange beams supporting a lightweight concrete slab on fluted light-
123 gage steel deck. The specimens are designed as one-way spanning partially composite beams per
124 AISC specifications [13]. The composite interface consists of headed shear studs that are welded
125 to the top of the beam and cast into the slab. The ends of the beam are connected to the support
126 frame using bolted shear tab connections. Partial restraint of the floor beam's thermal expansion
127 is provided by the support frame via those connections. A constant flexural load representing in-
128 situ gravity loading is applied with a hydraulic cylinder. One specimen has a layer of SFRM
129 (corresponding to a 2-hr prescriptive rating) applied to its steel beam and the other is unprotected.
130 The results of these tests, which are performed using the ASTM E119 standard fire curve, provide
131 deeper understanding of the thermo-mechanical response of composite floor assemblies to fire
132 considering partial restraint of thermal expansion and significantly different rates of temperature
133 increase in the beam. The results of these tests will demonstrate the value of using performance-
134 based calculations for translating fire resistance ratings into realistic predictions of structural
135 response.

136

137 2. Background

138 **Table 1** summarizes several previous experimental studies [8,19–24] that have examined
139 the thermo-mechanical response of one-way spanning composite floor beams subjected to gravity
140 load and fire. Most tests were performed in the general context of the ASTM E119 or ISO 834
141 standard fire test, though typically with some modification to either the support conditions or the
142 fire exposure. All tests discussed here used headed studs to achieve composite action between a
143 conventional wide-flange steel beam and concrete floor slab. Results of fire tests on composite
144 floor systems that utilize other steel elements such as cellular floor beams [25,26] and truss joists

145 [27,28] are also available in the existing literature but are considered to be outside the scope of
146 this study.

147 All studies except those by NIST [22–24] were performed on laboratory-scale specimens
148 (with spans less than 6 meters) and used various methods of flat slab construction. The NIST tests
149 were performed at a more realistic length of 12.8 meters with a profiled slab on fluted metal deck,
150 which is typical in current North American practice. Separate research by Mirza and Uy [29]
151 indicated that composite beams with solid flat slab configurations experience increased shear
152 demand and deformation in the stud connectors, whereas composite beams with profiled slabs on
153 fluted decks are better able to develop the full compressive capacity of the concrete and
154 demonstrate greater structural resistance to fire loading. The tests described in this paper were
155 designed to generate more data regarding the fire resistance of composite floor beams with slab on
156 fluted deck that are typical of current North American construction.

157 In general, the tests summarized in **Table 1** examined the impact of the following
158 parameters on the fire resistance of these specimens: the degree of composite action between the
159 beam and slab, the degree of axial and rotational restraint at the end connections, the level of
160 initially applied gravity load, and the impact of a cooling phase as the fire decays after reaching
161 peak exposure. Tests on protected specimens with at least a moderate amount of axial and
162 rotational restraint showed that the degree of composite action had little effect on the ultimate fire
163 resistance when subjected to the same loading and fire exposure [8,20]. Those specimens showed
164 minor slip in the shear studs as the restrained ends prevented excessive differential shear
165 displacement or thermal expansion between the beam and slab (which experience different rates
166 of temperature increase when subjected to the same heating due to significant differences in
167 thermal conductivity). Conversely, specimens that were unrestrained to thermal expansion, both

168 with and without passive fire protection, experienced more shear deformation at the studs due to
169 the lack of restraint to differential displacement between the beam and slab [19]. However, the fire
170 resistance and displacement time history of protected specimens with partial and full composite
171 action were nearly the same.

172 The NIST tests showed that slab continuity beyond the ends of a composite floor beam
173 with shear connections can enhance its fire resistance and enable an increase in ultimate deflection
174 [24]. Tests of composite beams that did not collapse during the initial heating phase and were then
175 allowed to cool during a “decay” phase (i.e. simulating a “natural” fire from ignition to burnout)
176 showed significant damage (including some fracture) to the shear connection plates and bolts
177 [21,24]. The study presented in this paper builds on the foundation laid by these previous studies
178 by providing a unique direct comparison of protected and unprotected composite beam specimens
179 (designed as partially composite per AISC specifications [13]) that are otherwise identical with
180 regards to their design, loading, and fire exposure.

Table 1. Summary of previous fire tests on one-way spanning composite floor beams.

Source	Span	Specimen Description	End Conditions	Protection	Fire Exposure
Ohio St. Univ., USA [8]	5.1 m	<i>BEAM:</i> 12WF27 <i>SLAB:</i> 102 mm flat slab <i>STUDS:</i> Length: 19 mm Spacing: 305 mm	Unrestrained in bearing (1 test), restrained with double angle connection (1 test)	22 mm Type MK SFRM on the beam, 13 mm on the underside of deck (1.5-2.5 hr rating)	ASTM E119 via furnace
CTICM, France [19]	4.9 m	<i>BEAM:</i> IPE300 <i>SLAB:</i> 120 mm flat slab <i>STUDS:</i> Length: 19 mm Spacing: 153 mm (4 tests), 305mm (1 test)	Simply supported beam with unrestrained slab	Unprotected (1 test); 25 mm mineral wool on the beam (4 tests)	ISO 834 via furnace
Tongji Univ., China [20]	5.26 m	<i>BEAM:</i> Welded H 320 mm×140 mm×8mm×10mm <i>SLAB:</i> 100 mm flat slab <i>STUDS:</i> Length: 19 mm Spacing: 188 mm (1 test), 376 mm (1 test)	Simply supported beam with unrestrained slab	11 mm SFRM on the beam	ISO 834 via furnace
Purdue Univ., USA [21]	3.67 m	<i>BEAM:</i> W10×22 (3 tests), W10×17 (1 test) <i>SLAB:</i> 88.9 mm flat slab <i>STUDS:</i> Length: 12.7 mm (3 tests), 15.9 mm (1 test) Spacing: 152 mm	Restrained with double angle (2 tests) or shear tab connections (2 tests)	Unprotected with slow slab heating to simulate a protected beam (2 tests); unprotected with faster slab heating to simulate an unprotected beam (2 tests)	Bottom flange and web heated at 7°C/min to 450-700°C with varied cooling procedures via an array of heating panels
NIST, USA [24]	12.8 m	<i>BEAM:</i> W18×35 <i>SLAB:</i> 83 mm on 77 mm profiled deck <i>STUDS:</i> 19 mm at 305 mm	Restrained double angle connection with slab restrained (1 test) or unrestrained (1 test)	SFRM at 2 hr rating on the beam, 3 hr rating on the connections	Parametric fire for compartment fuel loads between 550 MJ/m ² and 1100 MJ/m ² via custom enclosure with burners

183 The current UL catalog [5] provides no hourly ratings for unprotected composite floor
184 members; however, unprotected members are permitted by the International Building Code [1] for
185 some building constructions types such as IIB (which have less square footage, lower occupancy,
186 and less overall height) when sprinkler systems (i.e. active fire protection) are installed.
187 Understanding the fire resistance and structural-fire mechanics of unprotected composite beams
188 relative to the ASTM E119 rating system would enable structural engineers to estimate their
189 resilience to fires that are suppressed (fully or partially) or contained by sprinklers before being
190 extinguished. There has also been growing interest in decreasing or eliminating some of the passive
191 fire protection applied to secondary framing (i.e. the beams) in composite floor systems. By using
192 performance-based calculations, previous studies have weighed potential reductions in material
193 and labor for passive fire protection installation against potential increases in damage when the
194 floor system is subjected to a natural fire (which has a decay phase toward burnout and may also
195 be influenced by sprinkler suppression) [30]. The unprecedented full-scale fire tests at Cardington
196 [31,32] as well as subsequent **subassembly** fire tests [33–36] of composite floor systems showed
197 that bays with unprotected secondary beams, stiff protected perimeter framing, and approximately
198 square slab aspect ratios can develop two-way slab membrane action and maintain enough
199 structural integrity to avoid collapse when subjected to a natural fire. The collapse resistance of
200 these assemblies despite potentially elevated levels of damage is reliant on several parameters,
201 including the support provided to the slab boundary conditions, the geometry (thickness, span
202 aspect ratio, etc.) and reinforcement of the slab, and the integrity of the unprotected steel beam’s
203 connections at large rotations. **Experimental tests on a composite floor subassembly** by Wellman
204 et al. [37] showed that the composite slab was unable to prevent failure of an unprotected filler
205 beam due to inadequate slab thickness and stiffness in the perimeter framing. The prospect of

206 accounting for two-way action in the composite slab to enhance the fire resistance of these floor
207 systems is promising, and further investigation is needed to determine the influence of beam
208 spacing, perimeter framing support, slab characteristics, and connection detailing. However, the
209 evaluation of composite floor systems as one-way spanning elements provides a conservative
210 design basis and is an appropriate next step toward the implementation of performance-based
211 approaches from the current prescriptive design environment.

212

213 **3. Experimental Program**

214 *3.1 Test Setup*

215 Two experimental tests on one-way spanning composite beam specimens were performed
216 using a modular structural testing furnace at Lehigh University's ATLSS Engineering Research
217 Center. The sides of the furnace are panelized and can be reconfigured via bolted flange
218 connections to create a furnace hearth that can be sized appropriately for a given test [38]. The
219 furnace exterior and stiff self-reacting frame for supporting specimens are shown schematically in
220 **Fig. 1**, and the photos in **Fig. 2** show the front furnace face removed to reveal its interior. The
221 furnace shell is constructed of 9.525-mm (3/8-in.) thick steel plates, with the exterior surface (cold
222 face) stiffened by channels and angles. For this test program, the shell was configured to be 4.57-
223 m long, 1.83-m wide, and 2.13-m tall (15-ft. × 6-ft. × 7-ft.). The interior surface is lined with 152.4-
224 mm (6-in.) ceramic wool refractory tiles to prevent the escape of heat from the furnace.

225 For these tests, the composite floor specimen forms the lid of the furnace as shown in **Fig.**
226 **3**. The specimens span one-way and are supported by two W10×26 columns that span vertically
227 through the furnace. The ends of the support columns (outside the furnace) are connected to a
228 heavy self-reacting frame (which is aligned with the furnace's centerline) using pinned clevis

229 assemblies with high shear capacity (see Fig. 4). The bottom clevis is bolted directly to the frame,
 230 and the top clevis can slide vertically so that the columns' axial thermal expansion will be
 231 unrestrained (thus avoiding an unnecessary buildup of axial force in these elements during testing).
 232 Both the slab lid and the bottom of the furnace have cutouts to allow the columns to pass through
 233 without contact. All cutouts and the slab edges are loosely packed with ceramic wool insulation to
 234 mitigate heat loss and to allow the columns to deflect freely in the lateral direction as they restrain
 235 the axial thermal expansion of the specimen.
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237
 238 **Fig. 1.** Side-view schematic of the modular structural testing furnace (units in mm with US
 239 framing sizes).
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Fig. 2. Photos of the modular testing furnace with one face removed for specimen installation:
(a) isometric and (b) side views.

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Fig. 3. Top view schematic of the furnace with the composite slab lid (units in mm with US framing sizes).

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Fig. 4. Close-up of a pinned clevis at the base of the support column.

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Fig. 5. Photos of the modular testing furnace with all faces installed: (a) before and (b) after flue installation.

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The modular furnace uses two medium velocity pre-mixed Maxon Kinemax 75-mm (3-in.) Series G burners. Each burner has a capacity of 2.5 GJ/hr when fired on-ratio (i.e. with the proper

259 volume ratio of methane gas to air for perfect combustion with no leftover reactants). In general,
260 on-ratio firing is approximately 10:1 air-to-gas. The burners have a turndown ratio of 96:1,
261 meaning that each burner has a minimum capacity of 26 MJ/hr. This turndown ratio is important
262 for experiments that require less power [38]. **Fig. 2a** shows one of the burners when firing. Air is
263 supplied to the burners by a 3.73 kW (5 HP) blower, and natural gas is continuously supplied to
264 the burner control system by the ATLSS Center's main utility line. Combustion exhaust is
265 ventilated into the high-bay laboratory using an **insulated steel flue stack that is attached to East**
266 **face of the furnace as shown in Fig. 5**. The exhaust cools rapidly and is then vented from the high-
267 bay using several large ceiling fans. A digital, programmable temperature controller uses
268 thermocouple feedback to provide a user-specified time-temperature curve within the furnace.
269 More details on the furnace design can be found in [38,39].

270

271 *3.2 Specimens*

272 Two structurally identical specimens were fabricated using a **hot-rolled** W12×26 beam
273 (ASTM A992 with 345 MPa [50 ksi] yield strength [40]) at a length of 3.34 m (10'-11.5"). **Fig. 6**
274 shows the elevation schematic of the full specimen within the furnace, and **Fig. 7** shows pre-test
275 photos of the specimens installed in the test setup. The beam supports a typical floor slab with an
276 82.6-mm (3.25-in.) thickness on top of a 50.8-mm (2-in.) 18GA light-gage composite steel deck.
277 The deck flutes run perpendicular to the span of the beam. As shown previously in **Fig. 3**, the slab
278 is used to comprise the lid of the furnace and was therefore designed with a 142-cm (56-in.) width
279 and 416.6-cm (164-in.) total length. The slab utilizes lightweight concrete (LWC) with a tested
280 density of 1938 kg/m³ (121 pcf) and was designed with 27.5 MPa (4 ksi) nominal compressive
281 strength. The slab was placed from a single batch of concrete and allowed to cure at least six

282 months prior to the first test to allow adequate curing. The mix design for the LWC, which was
283 placed from the same batch, is summarized in **Table 2**. The slabs were covered with moist burlap
284 for two weeks after concrete placement, after which the burlap was removed and the slabs were
285 air-cured at ambient temperature and humidity within the ATLSS Lab until testing. Concrete
286 strength was obtained as the average of three cylinders tested at 28 days as well as on the test day
287 for each specimen: 25.9 MPa (3761 psi) at 28 days, 29.1 MPa (4227 psi) on the first test day, and
288 28.7 MPa (4163 psi) on the second test day.

289 Slab reinforcement (provided primarily to control cracking in the transverse direction)
290 consists of 6x6, 4GA welded wire reinforcement (WWR) placed 19.05-mm (3/4-in.) below the top
291 of the slab per minimum cover requirements [41]. A photo of the composite deck before concrete
292 placement, showing the WWR and shear studs, is provided in **Fig. 8**. The composite beam was
293 hoisted during installation using two steel tabs that were welded to the top flange of the beam and
294 extend through the top face of the slab as shown in **Fig. 6** and **Fig. 8**. During testing, a slightly
295 slack cable was run from each tab to the header of the self-reacting frame as a failsafe against
296 collapse. These cables remained slack throughout both tests.

297

298 **Fig. 6.** Elevation view schematic of the test specimen and support columns (units in mm with US
299 framing sizes).

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301

302 **Fig. 7.** Pre-test photos of the specimens installed in the test setup: (a) protected (prior to ceramic
303 blanket wrap being applied to the column, channels, and connection zone) and (b) unprotected
304 (after ceramic blanket wrap was applied)

Fig. 8. Isometric photo of the specimens before concrete placement.

Table 2. Concrete mix design

	Material	Saturated Surface Dry (SSD), kg (lbs)	Volume, m ³ (ft ³)
Cement:	Buzzi Unicem Type I Stockertown, PA	277 (610)	0.088 (3.10)
Fine Aggregate:	Sahara Sand, Inc. Williamstown, NJ	703 (1549)	0.265 (9.37)
Coarse Aggregate:	¾-in. – 785 lbs/yd oven dry Norlite Cohoes, NY (at 15% abs water)	392 (865)	0.242 (8.56)
Water:		138 (305)	0.138 (4.89)
Air:		4%	0.031 (1.08)
	TOTAL:	1510 (3329)	0.77 (27.0)
w/c:	0.50		
Slump, mm (in.):	127 (5.0)		
Unit weight, kg/m³ (pcf):	1938 (121)		
Admixture:	36.6 oz Daracem 55 W.R.		

This composite beam configuration is based on a typical floor system for a steel-framed office building, though the span was limited by the furnace dimensions. The composite beam is designed to be partially composite per AISC design specifications [13,42] using ten 19.05-mm (3/4-in.) diameter, 101.6-mm (4-in.) long shear studs that are spaced at 304.8-mm (1-ft.) on center and placed in the “weak” position within each flute of the metal deck. The specimens were calculated to be 23.6% composite at ambient temperature based on the nominal properties of the

316 concrete slab, steel beam, and the shear studs [43]. This level of composite action, which is similar
317 to that used in previous tests by Selden et al. [21] and Wellman et al. [37], suggests that the shear
318 studs would be the limiting element for ambient flexural capacity. The specimens in this study
319 were deliberately designed to have a low composite percentage to demonstrate the increases in
320 composite action when the assembly is heated. Previous tests by Wang et al. [20] showed that
321 partially composite beams behave increasingly composite (eventually reaching fully composite)
322 under fire exposure. The beam will experience a faster temperature increase than the slab when
323 subjected to the same fire exposure, thereby increasing the composite percentage as the beam
324 increasingly weakens relative to both the slab and the shear studs (which are partially protected
325 via their concrete embedment).

326 The beam is framed to the web of an orthogonal C15×40 channel at each end with a shear
327 tab connection, and the top flange of the beam is coped in accordance with the AISC specification
328 [13]. This beam-end configuration, illustrated in **Fig. 9**, emulates a typical beam-to-girder
329 connection, with the C15×40 posing as the girder and providing transverse vertical support to the
330 slab. The outside face of the channel web was bolted to the interior flange face of the W10×26
331 support columns as shown in **Fig. 9b**. An additional C6×10.5 was bolted to the opposite flange
332 face of the W10×26 column to provide transverse gravity support to the “wings” of the slab that
333 extend past the connection (which are included to complete the furnace lid). These slab wings are
334 free to displace upward as the beam deflects downward and its ends correspondingly rotate.

335 As configured in **Fig. 6**, the support column (with pinned ends due to the clevis
336 connections) provides an ambient stiffness of 56.9 kN/mm (325 kip/in) to resist horizontal
337 expansion of the heated specimens. This stiffness is approximately 25% of the 220 kN/mm (1256
338 kip/in) horizontal restraining stiffness reported from the results of NIST’s recent fire tests on long-

339 span composite floor beams [22–24], which were summarized previously in **Table 1**. The framing
 340 which provided that restraint in the NIST tests was located just outside the high-temperature
 341 chamber (with the beam end connections just inside the chamber) and therefore provided
 342 approximately constant resistance throughout those tests. In order to keep the beam’s end
 343 connections within the heated chamber for this study, the support columns had to pass through the
 344 furnace due to current constraints of the self-reacting frame. As a result, the columns do experience
 345 some increase in temperature during testing; however, as will be discussed below in Section 3.3,
 346 they were heavily wrapped with passive fire protection material to minimize their temperature
 347 increase and the resulting loss of restraining stiffness.

348
 349 **Fig. 9.** Shear tab connection details (units in mm): (a) side view and (b) facing the C15 × 40 web
 350

351 *3.3 Passive Fire Protection*

352 One specimen was protected with SFRM in accordance with the 2014 UL Design No. D902
 353 [44], which is commonly used in current steel building practice. A minimum thickness of 22.2-
 354 mm (7/8-in.) of CAFCO 300 [45] was applied to achieve a 2-hr rating for both a restrained
 355 assembly and unrestrained beam per Section 6C of the D902 design [44] and the SFRM thickness
 356 conversion equations provided in ASCE 29-05 [9]. Calculations for the SFRM thickness

357 conversion are provided in [43]. CAFCO 300 is a low density commercial product with posted
358 density of 240 kg/m^3 (15 pcf) and thermal conductivity of 0.078 W/m-K at ambient temperature
359 (24°C). Temperature dependent material properties are not available from the manufacturer, but
360 several studies have examined the changes in density, thermal conductivity, and specific heat in
361 low density SFRM materials for a range of high temperatures that are typical of fire exposure
362 [46,47].

363 All thermocouples were attached to both bare steel specimens, and the SFRM was then
364 applied to one specimen by experienced professional installers 152 days prior to the first test to
365 allow adequate curing. The SFRM was applied while the beam was supported in a separate
366 elevated framing rig directly adjacent to the test setup – the specimen was then carefully hoisted
367 into place for testing one month after application. The second specimen was left unprotected (i.e.
368 bare steel). The 82.6-mm (3.25-in.) thickness of the LWC topping slab met the minimum
369 requirement of the D902 design [44]. As shown in **Fig. 7**, no SFRM was intentionally applied to
370 the underside of the fluted deck of either specimen. For the protected specimen, a minor amount
371 of SFRM overshot onto the deck, as is typical during field installation.

372 As shown in **Fig. 10**, the support framing elements located inside the furnace (i.e. the
373 transverse channels and the $\text{W}10 \times 26$ columns) were double-wrapped with ceramic wool blankets
374 to mitigate their temperature increase during the fire tests (since their performance is not the
375 primary focus of the test). A single wrap of ceramic wool blanket was also applied to the shear tab
376 connection zone and extended roughly 355-mm (14-in.) from the end of the beam to mitigate the
377 temperature increase of the connection. Section 704.3 of the 2018 International Building Code [1]
378 states that connections from primary framing to any secondary structural member must be given
379 the same passive fire protection as required for the primary framing. In an actual structure, the

380 composite floor beam's end connections would therefore receive the same hourly rating as the
381 supporting girder. This approach prevents secondary elements from becoming connection critical
382 due to severe temperature-induced weakening, while also ensuring that a secondary element
383 doesn't excessively conduct heat to the primary framing. Applying a single wrap of ceramic wool
384 blanket to the connection zone simulates this requirement while still allowing some increase in the
385 connection temperature as if it were sprayed with SFRM. SFRM was not directly applied to the
386 connection or the support framing once the specimen was installed due to space limitations and
387 the impracticality of cleanup inside the furnace. All ceramic wool blankets were secured using
388 light wire ties, all of which remained intact and in-place during both tests.

389
390 **Fig. 10.** Photo of the wrapped connection zone at the end of the unprotected specimen.
391

392 *3.4 Applied Loading*

393 As shown in **Fig. 11**, the specimens were loaded in four-point bending at their third-points
394 in order to approximate the moment diagram due to a uniformly distributed load. Loading was
395 applied via a long-stroke single-acting hydraulic cylinder that was inversely mounted to the
396 underside of the large header beam of the self-reacting frame (see **Fig. 1**). The cylinder exerted
397 force onto a loading tree comprised of W8×67 beams. The bottom skids of the loading tree had a

398 transverse length of 122-cm (4-ft.) with halved-pipe sections (165.1-mm [6.5-in.] outer diameter)
399 welded to the bottom face of the bottom flange. This skid design eliminated sharp edges and
400 mitigated excessive cracking or punching in the top face of the slab due to load concentration. As
401 fire-induced deflections increased, the rounded contact surface allowed the lines of load
402 application to “roll” with the specimen and maintain a consistent longitudinal position. Applying
403 the load over the width of the composite slab via the skids mitigated the potential for the
404 longitudinal edges of the slab to pucker as the beam deflected downward.

405
406 **Fig. 11.** Specimen loading setup (units in mm): (a) side-view schematic and (b) isometric photo

407
408 Recall that ASTM E119 states that loaded floor assembly specimens should be tested with
409 the “maximum-load condition allowed under nationally recognized structural design criteria unless
410 limited design criteria are specified and a corresponding reduced load is applied” [2]. The UL
411 D902 assembly, similar to others in the UL catalog, does not explicitly state what load level was
412 used to develop its listed hourly ratings. In practice, composite floors will be designed to meet
413 both strength and serviceability requirements for a combination of dead load (DL) and live load
414 (LL). If using allowable stress design (ASD), the nominal moment capacity must be at least 1.67
415 times the applied moment from the DL+LL “maximum service” load combination, which could
416 conservatively be assumed to be present during a fire. If using load and resistance factor design
417 (LRFD), the nominal moment capacity of the composite flexural cross-section (with a 10%

418 reduction) at ambient conditions must exceed the applied moment induced by 1.2DL+1.6LL.
419 When designing for fire, the LRFD approach per ASCE 7-16 [14] allows the “extreme” load
420 combination of 1.2DL+0.5LL to account for realistically reduced live load during typical in-
421 service conditions. Beam depth, the percentage of composite action, slab thickness, deck flute
422 depth, and camber are selected to ensure that deflection limit requirements (typically span/240 for
423 service conditions and span/360 for LL only) are met for composite designs that efficiently meet
424 the strength requirements.

425 When applied in practice, the ASD approach will utilize up to 60% of a composite beam’s
426 nominal moment capacity depending on its flexural stiffness and camber to meet deflection limit
427 requirements. Likewise, the LRFD approach can utilize approximately 35-65% of the factored
428 nominal moment capacity depending on deflection limitations with the assumption of simply
429 supported boundary conditions (as is typical for secondary floor beams), uniformly distributed
430 load (including self-weight, superimposed DL, and LL of 2.4 to 4.8 kPa [50 to 100 psf]), and
431 tributary widths common to most composite floors in steel buildings (e.g. 4.6 to 9.2 meters [15 to
432 30 ft]). Preliminary numerical simulations were performed for the protected specimen (numerical
433 simulations are discussed in the Part 2 companion paper of this study [18]) to determine an applied
434 load level that would exceed 2 hrs of fire resistance based on the ASTM E119 deflection limits.
435 Based on these calculations, a 158-kN (35.5-kip) applied load from the hydraulic cylinder (evenly
436 split between each skid) in combination with the specimen self-weight (3.27 kN/m [224 plf])
437 would utilize 35% of the composite section’s factored nominal moment capacity (calculated as
438 $\phi M_n = 266.1$ kN-m [196.3 kip-ft], where $\phi=0.9$ [13,42]). Calculations of the composite section
439 moment capacity are provided in [43]. Both the protected and unprotected specimens were tested
440 under this constant load, which represents a lower-bound application of the LRFD extreme load

441 combination. Numerical simulations discussed in Part 2 of this study will examine the structural
442 fire resistance of these specimens relative to both the 35% as-tested and a 65% utilization of
443 factored nominal moment capacity, with the latter representing both an LRFD extreme load upper
444 bound as well as an ASD maximum service condition [18].

445

446 *3.5 Instrumentation*

447 **Fig. 12** shows the instrumentation layout for both specimens. In each test, 54 Type-K
448 thermocouples were used to measure the temperature of the specimen as well as the furnace
449 chamber. Steel temperatures at the bottom flange, web, and top flange were taken at three section
450 locations along the length of the beam to monitor for any longitudinal variation in heating. The
451 shear tab connections had a total of 10 thermocouples to monitor the tab plate, its weld to the
452 supporting channel, and the bolts. The temperature of the support columns was recorded using 12
453 thermocouples near the connection and at column mid-height. Additional thermocouples were
454 provided on the column end clevises and the cold face of the furnace for monitoring purposes. **Six**
455 **type-K thermocouples were placed within the furnace about 30 cm (1 ft) from the insulated lining**
456 **(three each at the top and bottom; two each at the North, South, and middle) to monitor its internal**
457 **temperature distribution.** Five thermocouples were applied to the top of slab in both tests to
458 measure heat transmission, and the unprotected test also included two additional thermocouples
459 on the underside of the steel deck. A high-temperature probe camera was inserted through a small
460 hole in the furnace wall to observe and record the specimen response during the test.

461 Two string potentiometers (straddling the loading tree) were used to measure vertical
462 displacement at midspan, and another two measured vertical displacement near the columns. The
463 horizontal column deflection due to specimen thermal expansion was measured using two

464 displacement transducers that were aligned with the longitudinal centerline of the beam. Since the
465 anchor point at the outside face of the support column was located within the furnace, rods heavily
466 wrapped in ceramic blankets were connected to the column and then passed through a small hole
467 in the furnace wall to the transducer.

468

469 3.6 Test Procedure

470 Prior to each test, the specimen was installed in the test setup under its self weight and
471 instrumented. To start each test, data acquisition is initiated and the hydraulic cylinder load is
472 applied gradually over 15 minutes under ambient conditions until the full test load is reached. With
473 constant loading applied throughout the test, the ASTM E119 standard fire curve (see Fig. 13) is
474 then applied via the two burners until the specimen exhibits “failure” via near total loss of flexural
475 resistance toward runaway downward deflection. The burners are then turned off, the applied load
476 is removed, and the specimen is allowed to cool naturally (i.e. there was no decay phase
477 programmed into this fire curve).

478 For tests of loaded restrained specimens, the ASTM E119 standard states that “the test
479 specimen shall have sustained the applied load during the classification period” [2] – in this study,
480 the time to runaway deflection will be regarded as meeting this criteria. Loaded unrestrained
481 specimens are rated according to two deflection limits: maximum deflection equal to $\frac{L_c^2}{400d}$ or a
482 maximum deflection rate (over one minute time intervals) equal to $\frac{L_c^2}{9000d}$, where L_c is the clear span
483 of the member and d is the distance between the extreme fibers of the composite beam in
484 compression and tension. These limits are also checked for each test since the specimens are
485 partially restrained. The value for d is commonly taken as the depth of only the steel beam for non-
486 composite floor beam assemblies and includes the slab thickness and depth of the fluted deck for

487 fully composite assemblies [48] . For this study, the depth of the steel beam (309.9-mm [12.2-in])
488 is used for d since the specimen is only 23.6% composite. A smaller value of d provides a slightly
489 more liberal deflection criteria which more closely corresponds to the loss of flexural resistance
490 observed in both tests. The deflection limits for the tested specimens (with L_c equal to 3.32-m
491 [130.9-in]) were therefore calculated to be 89.0-mm (3.51-in.) and 3.96 mm/min (0.16 in/min),
492 respectively.

493

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495

496

Fig. 12. Instrumentation layout: (a) full assembly, (b) connection region, (c) typical beam section, and (d) top of slab

497 **4. Test Results**

498 *4.1 Furnace Temperatures*

499 A plot of all internal furnace temperatures from both tests is provided in **Fig. 13**, with the
500 average shown as a thicker line. The protected specimen was tested for 138 minutes before it
501 began to deflect rapidly downward toward runaway failure and the burners were shut off. That
502 specimen reached the ASTM E119 unrestrained maximum deflection limit at 130 minutes.
503 Likewise, the unprotected specimen was tested for 28 minutes before approaching runaway and
504 reached the maximum deflection limit at 22 minutes. The time needed to reach these milestones
505 **as well as the steel thermal limiting criterion** is summarized in **Table 3**.

506 **Table 3.** Time (in minutes) needed to reach various failure criteria

Specimen	ASTM E119 Rating	Tested Failure Time (by Runaway Deflection)	ASTM E119 Unrestrained Criteria		
			By Deflection Limits	By Max. Temp. Limit (704°C [1300°F])	By Avg. Temp. Limit (593°C [1100°F])
Protected	120	138	130	96	88
Unprotected	N/A	28	22	16	12

507

508 **Fig. 13** shows that the internal furnace temperatures were relatively uniform during both
509 tests and closely followed the ASTM E119 standard curve. According to the **ASTM** E119 standard
510 [2], the area under the net temperature time history from the test (up to furnace shutdown) cannot
511 deviate from the area under **the standard** curve by more than 5% for a test longer than 2 hours,
512 7.5% for a test duration between 1-2 hours, and 10% for a test of one hour or less. Both tests met
513 this criteria, with the furnace curve slightly higher (+1.41% and +8.78% for the protected and
514 unprotected tests, respectively) than the standard curve.

515

516

517

Fig. 13. Internal furnace temperatures for the (a) protected and (b) unprotected tests

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519 4.2 Experimental Observations

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The protected specimen was tested 182 days after its concrete slab was placed, and no concrete spalling or excessive cracking occurred during the test. Slight popping noises were heard about 15 minutes after the start of heating, presumably due to differential thermal expansion between the metal deck and the slab. Wet spots appeared on the top of the slab from 15-40 minutes into the test as moisture in the concrete was pushed upward through its pores toward the free surface from its heated underside. As observed via the probe camera, the SFRM on the beam remained intact until about 2 minutes prior to the end of the test and burner shutdown, at which time the specimen was approaching runaway deflection. At that time (~136 minutes into the test), the SFRM underneath the North loading skid began to visibly crack, with a small chunk falling from the bottom flange and larger pieces falling from the top flange. The test was halted after the rate and magnitude of beam deflection subsequently increased (with the final deflection just reaching 200 mm [8 in.]). No audible or visible signs of connection fracture or sudden slab cracking occurred during the test.

533

534

Post-test photos of the protected specimen in **Fig. 14** (while still installed in the test assembly with the front wall of the furnace removed) show the aftermath of the SFRM damage

535 that occurred just prior to furnace shutdown. The slab exhibited transverse crack lines at the
536 loading skid locations (**Fig. 14b**) but was otherwise intact despite the significant downward
537 deflection. The shear tab connection showed some permanent rotation with no visible fracture in
538 the tab plate or its weld to the channel face. All bolts in both connections experienced permanent
539 shear deformation (with the top bolts fracturing) but remained in place as shown in **Fig. 14c**.
540 Photos of the disassembled beam in **Fig. 15** show some minor warping in the bolt holes on the
541 beam web – the thicker tab plate showed negligible warping.

542 After the specimen was disassembled from the test setup, the SFRM was removed and the
543 beam was visually inspected. **Fig. 15** shows that the beam experienced negligible local buckling,
544 and the bottom flange remained nearly straight with only minor lateral displacement. There was
545 no visual evidence of de-bonding of the deck from the slab, and shear slippage between the beam
546 and composite slab at each of the shear stud locations was visually negligible. The support columns
547 experienced some permanent flexural deflection and were replaced for the subsequent test of the
548 unprotected specimen. There were no signs of contact from the bottom flange of the beam on the
549 interior flange face of either support column. The transverse channels showed no visible permanent
550 deformation and were reused in the unprotected test.

551

552
553

Fig. 14. Protected specimen post-test photos: assembled

554
555

Fig. 15. Protected specimen post-test photos: disassembled

556 The unprotected specimen was tested 255 days after the concrete was placed, and again,
557 no concrete spalling or excessive cracking occurred during the test. Wet spots were visible on the
558 concrete after about 20 minutes of heating, and popping could be heard throughout the test, with
559 the frequency of popping increasing in the final 5 minutes before shutdown. The test was stopped
560 when the specimen's rate of deflection began to significantly increase toward runaway (with the
561 final deflection just reaching 200 mm [8 in.]). As shown in **Fig. 16**, the slab had relatively few
562 cracks visible on its top face except for large transverse cracks below the loading skids. The shear
563 tab connections remained intact similar to the protected specimen. All bolts in both connections
564 showing some shear deformation with no fracture (**Fig. 16c**), and some warping occurred in the
565 beam web bolt holes (**Fig. 17**). The thicker shear tab showed negligible warping with no signs of
566 fracture at its weld to the channel. As with the protected specimen, the unprotected specimen
567 showed no visual evidence of de-bonding between the deck and slab, and shear slippage between
568 the beam and composite slab at each of the shear stud locations was visually negligible. The
569 support columns and transverse channels all showed no visible permanent deformation and could
570 potentially be reused in future tests.

571 As observed via the probe camera, the bottom flange of the unprotected beam began to
572 experience slight lateral displacement (similar in magnitude to the final state of the protected beam)
573 about three minutes prior to the end of the test. The lateral displacement then accelerated during
574 the last minute of the test toward runaway, resulting in the final deformed shape shown in **Fig. 17**.
575 Besides these deformations, the beam also exhibited slight signs of local instability in the bottom
576 flange and web just past the end of the ceramic blanket wrap toward the connections. However,
577 post-test inspection of the column again showed no visible signs of contact between the bottom
578 flange of the beam and the column face. **Fig. 17** shows that the ends of the bottom flange

579 experienced some rotation about the vertical axis, which would not have been possible had it been
580 jammed against the face of the column. **Fig. 17** also shows the emergence of fracture at the
581 interface of the web and bottom flange at the North end of the beam, most likely due to the
582 differential thermal expansion and torsion between these plates as the beam approached runaway.

583

584 *4.3 Thermal Response*

585 The beam temperatures resulting from exposure to the fire temperatures in **Fig. 13** are plotted
586 in **Fig. 18** through **Fig. 20**, including all thermocouples at each of the three longitudinal locations.
587 Maximum temperatures in both beams reached 800-850°C (1472-1562°F) just before burner
588 shutdown. The temperatures in the unprotected beam are more closely banded than for the
589 protected beam since the unprotected flange and web plates all heat up more rapidly with direct
590 exposure to high temperature. The gradient between the flanges of the unprotected beam
591 approaches only 93°C (200°F) during the test, with the bottom flange reaching higher temperature
592 due to more exposed surface area. The unprotected beam also cools faster following burner
593 shutdown since it has no SFRM, which slows the cooling rate of the protected specimen. The
594 protected beam develops a significant thermal gradient up to almost 204°C (400°F) between the
595 top and bottom flanges at all three longitudinal locations. The web temperature in the protected
596 test trends toward that of the bottom flange, while the top flange benefits from having SFRM
597 applied not only to its own surfaces but also infilled into the fluted gaps between its top surface
598 and the underside of the fluted slab deck. All three plots for the protected beam show a modest
599 spike in top flange temperature near the end of the test as the SFRM became cracked (and in some
600 cases, dislodged) due to increased beam deflection and prolonged heat exposure.

601

602

603
604 **Fig. 16.** Unprotected specimen post-test photos: assembled

605

606

Fig. 17. Unprotected specimen post-test photos: disassembled

607
608

Fig. 18. South end beam temperatures for the (a) protected and (b) unprotected specimens

609
610

Fig. 19. Midspan beam temperatures for the (a) protected and (b) unprotected specimens

611

Fig. 20. North end beam temperatures for the (a) protected and (b) unprotected specimens

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The ASTM E119 standard states that an hourly rating for an unrestrained steel beam can be determined as the time at which either of the two following thermal limits are reached: maximum temperature of 704°C (1300°F) or average temperature of 593°C (1100°F) [2]. As shown in **Fig. 18** through **Fig. 20**, the maximum temperature in both specimens occurred in the bottom flange, though the web temperatures were very similar. The times at which the two tested beams reached each thermal limit are summarized in **Table 3**. The results show that the protected

620 specimen nearly achieved a 1.5-hr resistance rating per the minimum thermal limit criteria. The
621 unprotected specimen reaches a 12-min rating per these thermal limits.

622 Of the five thermocouples placed on top of the slab, two in each test failed to maintain
623 contact with the slab surface and did not yield usable data. In both tests, however, the
624 thermocouples at the quarter points consistently recorded data and are presented here for
625 comparison between specimens. One was placed above the thin section of the fluted slab, and the
626 other was placed above the thick section. The unprotected test also had two thermocouples on the
627 bottom of the deck, with one each at the thin and thick sections. **Fig. 21** shows that, as expected,
628 the top of slab heated slightly faster over the thin sections than over the thick sections. **ASTM**
629 **E119 specifies a maximum temperature of 139°C (250°F) for an unexposed floor slab surface in**
630 **addition to the steel beam thermal criteria discussed previously. The top of slab in the protected**
631 **test reached this thermal criteria at 108-min (20-min after the beam average temperature was**
632 **reached), and the unprotected test remained below this limit for the full duration of the test.** The
633 thermocouples on the slab bottom of the unprotected specimen were placed on the underside of
634 the metal deck, which would be expected to have higher temperature than if they were embedded
635 in the concrete. The bottom of slab temperatures in **Fig. 21b** follow a similar trend as the beam
636 temperatures shown in **Fig. 18b** through **Fig. 20b** at roughly 20% lower magnitude. The spike in
637 the “thin bottom” temperature around 27-30 minutes is most likely due to a loss of contact between
638 the thermocouple and the deck.

639
640 **Fig. 21.** Slab temperatures for the (a) protected and (b) unprotected specimens
641

642 As shown in **Fig. 22**, peak temperatures measured throughout the shear tab connection
643 ranged from 575-650°C (1067-1202°F) for the protected specimen and 175-225°C (347-437°F)
644 for the unprotected specimen. Higher temperatures were experienced in the protected specimen
645 due to prolonged heating and conduction through the ceramic fiber blanket wrap, with both
646 specimens experiencing a similar rate of connection temperature increase. Even though both beams
647 experienced similar temperature increases along their spans, conduction along the length of the
648 beam toward the cooler blanket wrapped connection zone was not sufficient to increase the
649 connection temperature of the unprotected beam to a similar range as for the protected beam.
650 Despite their temperature difference, both specimens experienced relatively similar levels of
651 permanent deformation in their connection components (as shown previously in **Fig. 15** and **Fig.**
652 **17**) while reaching similar final deflections around 200 mm (8 in.) (and thus reaching similar
653 connection rotation). The most significant difference is that the top bolts in the protected test
654 fractured due to their higher temperature and corresponding loss of shear strength.

655
656 **Fig. 22.** Connection zone temperatures for the (a) protected and (b) unprotected specimens
657

658 **Fig. 23** shows that the support columns experienced significant increases in temperature
659 even though they were double-wrapped with the ceramic fiber blanket. The trend and magnitude
660 of the column temperatures are similar to those measured in the connection zone, although with
661 greater variability. Temperatures measured near the column mid-height were tightly banded (with
662 peak values near 600°C [1112°F] in the protected test and 200°C [392°F] in the unprotected test)
663 and showed negligible gradient between the flanges. Temperatures measured at the same height as
664 the beam connection showed greater variation due to the congestion of the connected elements. As
665 mentioned previously, the support columns from the protected test suffered permanent lateral
666 deformation by restraining the thermal expansion of the composite beam specimen. According to
667 Appendix 4 of AISC 360-16 [13], the columns in those tests had lost roughly 50% of yield strength
668 and 70% of stiffness at the peak temperatures shown in **Fig. 23** – the onset of permanent flexural
669 deformation is therefore not surprising. The columns in the unprotected test experienced much
670 lower peak temperatures and would have only experienced an approximate stiffness loss of 10%
671 with no loss of strength, thereby enabling flexural response with no visible permanent deformation.
672 The column temperatures in **Fig. 23** are used as input for the numerical models of these tests,
673 which are presented in the Part 2 companion paper [18].

674

675 **Fig. 23.** Column temperatures for the (a) protected and (b) unprotected specimens

676

677 *4.3 Structural Performance*

678 The displacement time histories measured during each test per the instrumentation map in
 679 **Fig. 12** are plotted in **Fig. 24** (with each curve representing the average of the individual
 680 North/South or East/West measurements). The midspan deflections of the two composite beam
 681 specimens in **Fig. 24a** have very similar trends and magnitudes, with both nearly reaching the same
 682 maximum deflection and the same peak deflection rate just before the burners were shut off. In
 683 **Fig. 24b**, the protected specimen induced nearly 50% more horizontal pushout on the support
 684 column than the unprotected specimen. Versus the unprotected test, both the column and the slab
 685 in the protected test reached higher temperatures due to longer heat exposure. The slab therefore
 686 provided more thermal expansion in conjunction with the protected beam, and the column offered
 687 less resistance to that specimen's thermal expansion due to losses in strength and stiffness. The
 688 horizontal column deflections show that both specimens continued to push outward until
 689 approaching runaway deflection. These displacements did not reverse direction until after the
 690 burners were shut off and the applied load was removed, indicating that the specimens did not
 691 transition under load to a catenary response after the loss of flexural resistance. Limitations on the
 692 stroke of the hydraulic cylinder as well as the risk of damaging the furnace prevented a

693 continuation of loading beyond flexural runaway to see whether the catenary transition would be
694 possible. Numerical modeling in the Part 2 companion paper [18] will explore whether this
695 transition would be theoretically possible with the tested assembly. The introduction of slab
696 continuity and the consideration of longer spans (which would develop larger deflections before
697 total loss of flexural stiffness) would potentially enable a post-flexural mode of structural response
698 and will be a focus of future phases of this project.

699

700 **Fig. 24.** Measured displacements: (a) vertical deflection of the beam at midspan and (b) average
701 horizontal pushout per **Fig. 12**

702

703 As summarized previously in **Table 3**, the protected specimen exceeds a 2-hr rating per
704 **ASTM E119** deflection limits when tested at a level of applied load that utilizes 35% of factored
705 nominal moment capacity (i.e. the LRFD extreme load lower bound). An increase in load toward
706 a maximum service load condition would invariably decrease the fire resistance rating below 2
707 hrs, potentially trending **toward the rating corresponding to** the thermal limits. The unprotected
708 specimen is able to nearly double its thermally limited fire resistance duration by instead using the
709 structural deflection limits, but again at the lower bound load level. Part 2 of this study [18] will
710 demonstrate the value of using performance-based numerical analysis to predict the structural fire
711 resistance of these composite floor beam specimens. In practice, validated modeling approaches
712 could be used to predict the thermo-mechanical response for multiple load levels and determine

713 SFRM thicknesses needed to meet a target fire resistance rating and/or withstand exposure to a
714 realistic fire until burnout or sprinkler suppression. Models could also include realistic structural
715 characteristics such as span length and slab continuity to tailor the fire resistance objectives to an
716 actual floor system.

717 In Fig. 25, the vertical midspan deflections of the composite beam specimens are plotted
718 as a function of the bottom flange (maximum) temperature and average beam temperature. The
719 temperature of each flange and the web are calculated as an average from all corresponding
720 thermocouple locations along the beam length, and the average temperature of the beam cross-
721 section is calculated as a weighted average based on the cross-sectional area of each plate
722 component. For comparison, the plots also include the corresponding ASTM E119 steel thermal
723 limits of maximum single location temperature of 704°C (1300°F) and maximum beam average
724 temperature of 593°C (1100°F) [2]. Both specimens exhibit very similar behavior, indicating that
725 their responses are primarily governed by their beam temperatures (which are similar) rather than
726 the temperatures in the composite slab, connections, or the restraining elements (which are
727 significantly different). Both specimens are able to reach runaway failure displacement at
728 temperatures that exceed the ASTM E119 thermal limits at the lower bound load level. Modeling
729 performed in Part 2 of this study will examine the relationship of midspan displacement versus
730 beam temperature for a maximum service load condition, with the goal of demonstrating the utility
731 of the thermal limit criteria as an indicator of structural resistance for composite floor systems
732 under fire.

733
 734 **Fig. 25.** Midspan vertical deflection versus (a) bottom flange (i.e. maximum) and (b) beam
 735 average temperature

736 The deflected shape of the protected specimen in Fig. 15, which showed little evidence of
 737 local or lateral flange instability, suggests that the flexural failure mode of this specimen was
 738 primarily a plastic mechanism of the composite section, particularly the steel beam. Numerical
 739 modeling in Part 2 of this study [18] further investigated whether the lateral instability of the
 740 bottom flange in the unprotected specimen, as shown previously in Fig. 17, contributed to its
 741 flexural failure. Using the temperatures measured from these tests as the thermal input, a shell
 742 element model of the composite steel beam and slab assembly was developed and provided
 743 conservatively accurate predictions of the temperature-induced deflections and the time to flexural
 744 failure for both the protected and unprotected specimens. The shell model also matched the
 745 experimental results by exhibiting significant lateral sway of the bottom flange for the unprotected
 746 case but very little sway for the protected case. In both cases, however, the axial stress in the
 747 bottom flange remained in tension at midspan and experienced only a very small amount of
 748 compression at the end of the beam throughout the simulations to flexural failure. To further
 749 examine the potential for lateral-torsional buckling, a second simulation of the unprotected model
 750 was performed with the bottom flange laterally braced at midspan. The results of this model were
 751 nearly identical to that of the as-tested model of the unprotected specimen with the bottom flange

752 unbraced. This result, combined with the lack of large bottom flange compression in all shell
753 element models, suggested that the lateral instability of the bottom flange did not govern the
754 flexural failure of the unprotected specimen and was caused by post-plastic instability rather than
755 a lateral-torsional mechanism.

756

757 5. Summary and Conclusions

758 A pair of partially restrained, partially composite steel floor beam specimens were
759 flexurally loaded and subjected to the ASTM E119 standard fire [2] in a large modular furnace at
760 Lehigh University's ATLSS Laboratory. The specimens were structurally identical and
761 representative of North American steel building construction practice, each consisting of a wide-
762 flange W12×26 steel beam that supported a reinforced LWC slab on fluted metal deck. The ends
763 of the beam were connected to a support frame via realistic shear tab connections with three bolts
764 each. The slab edges were unrestrained to rotation, but the axial expansion of the heated specimens
765 was partially restrained via the flexural stiffness of a supporting column at both ends. One
766 specimen was coated with spray-applied fire resistive material (SFRM) corresponding to a 2-hr
767 fire resistance rating per UL Design D902 [44] – the SFRM thickness was calculated via
768 conversion equations provided in ASCE 29-05 [9]. The other specimen was left unprotected (i.e.
769 as bare steel). The specimens were intentionally designed to have a relatively low level of
770 composite action between the beam and slab via embedded shear studs, with the goal of
771 demonstrating composite action in flexural response to fire.

772 Based on the results of this study, the following conclusions can be made:

- 773 1. The fundamental structural mechanics of one-way spanning composite floor beams in a fire
774 are primarily dependent on the temperature of the beam. Both the protected and unprotected

775 specimens exhibited similar structural response as a function of beam temperature despite
776 having different temperature increases in their composite slab, connection, the support frame
777 (due to significantly different durations of fire exposure until failure).

778 2. Neither shear slip nor localized cracking could be visibly detected at the composite stud
779 locations during post-test inspection, indicating that the specimens were able to utilize
780 composite action in their flexural resistance to fire.

781 3. The shear tab connections for both specimens were covered with fire protection at a level
782 similar to the supporting columns, which is consistent with fire protection guidelines in the
783 International Building Code [1]. Connections for both specimens experienced permanent
784 deformation and some shear damage to the bolts. However, all shear tab connections
785 maintained adequate integrity such that both specimens reached runaway flexural failure. The
786 protected specimen developed higher connection temperatures due to longer fire exposure and
787 consequently suffered fracture in its top bolts in the shear tab connection. The unprotected
788 specimen experienced no bolt fracture.

789 4. The protected specimen nearly reached a 1.5-hr fire resistance rating per ASTM E119 thermal
790 limit criteria. The specimen exceeded a 2-hr fire resistance per ASTM E119 deflection limit
791 criteria when loaded to a level that represented 60% of a maximum service load condition (i.e.
792 a lower bound application of the ASCE 7-16 extreme load combination for LRFD). Applying
793 a maximum service load condition would have invariably resulted in a fire resistance time less
794 than 2 hrs per the deflection limit criteria.

795 5. The unprotected specimen reached the thermal limit criteria after only 12 minutes of fire
796 exposure but reached runaway midspan deflection just short of 30 minutes at the same lower
797 bound load. Depending on load level, fire severity, and boundary conditions, unprotected

798 composite floor beams in one-way bending may offer some structural resistance to fire
799 exposure, which could be appropriately utilized via a performance-based design approach.

800 The data obtained from this test series is used to validate both complex and simplified
801 modeling predictions in a subsequent companion paper [18], with the goal of demonstrating the
802 ability of those models to accurately and conservatively predict the response and failure modes of
803 the tested composite floor assemblies when subjected to a standard fire exposure. Variations in
804 load and SFRM thickness are then analyzed to further examine the relationship between deflection-
805 based and thermally-based limit criteria to quantify structural fire resistance. In future work, these
806 models **could** be leveraged to evaluate composite steel floor beam assemblies for their resilience
807 to realistic fire scenarios that include burnout.

808

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821 **7. References**

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